

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight A431

27 October 1995

ACSOE Orientation Flight

For more information contact:

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FLIGHT FOLDER

DATE: 27 / 10 / 95 TAKE OFF 0955 H (local time) FLIGHT NO. A 431
LANDING 1225

PROJECT OFFICER:

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST: A. KAYE

FLIGHT LEADER: M. RULE

OBSERVER:

OTHERS: OZONE { J. KENT
PEROXIDE { K. DEWEY
B. BANDY (SF26)

CAPTAIN: M. PURSE
CO-PILOT: C. O'BRIEN
NAVIGATOR: J. CANNING
ENGINEER: K. QUICK
LOADMASTER: J. AYERS

+ 5 x SF26 from NERC

TRIALS INSTRUCTION (s):

OPERATING AREA:

WEYBOURNE

GENERAL SYNOPTIC SITUATION:

TIME:

A431 27th October, 1995

<u>Start</u> TIME (EM)	<u>End</u> TIME (EM)		<u>HEIGHT</u>	<u>HDG</u>
095705		Take off from BOSCOMBE		
101721(15)-103315(17)		Profile P1	FL150->1000ft	060 deg
103432(18)-103643(19)		Profile P1	1000ft->50ft	030 deg
104428(20)-104920(21)		Run 1	100ft	355 deg
104920(21)-104940		Profile P2.1	100ft->200ft	355 deg
105158(22)-105658(23)		Run 2	200ft	200 deg
105658(23)-105727(24)		Profile P2.2	200ft->500ft	200 deg
105848(25)-110349(26)		Run 3	500ft	350 deg
110349(26)-110433(27)		Profile P2.3	500ft->1000ft	350 deg
110551(28)-111055(29)		Run 4	1000ft	180 deg
111055(29)-111325(30)		Profile P2.4	1000ft->4000ft	180 deg
111448(31)-111542(32)		Profile P2.4	4000ft->5000ft	355 deg
111542(32)-112059(33)		Run 5	5000ft	345 deg
112059(33)-112247(34)		Profile P2.5	5000ft->7000ft	345 deg
112352(35)-112638(36)		Profile P2.5	7000ft->FL100	170 deg

Abort Run 6 and descend to 4000ft due to cracked window on flight deck
Transit back to Boscombe at FL60

122148 Land at BOSCOMBE

MRF07 Joint Operation Logistics Learning Instructional Exercise

Date: 27/10/95 Flight No: A431

- **SORTIE OBJECTIVE:** To familiarise the ACSOE core group with MRF experimental flying. To obtain Ozone and Hydrocarbon bottle profiles over or near the Weybourne Atmospheric Observatory.
- **LOCATION:** North of Weybourne Atmospheric Observatory (Latitude 52°57'N, Longitude 1°7'E)
- **WEATHER:** Not critical
- **FLIGHT PATTERN:**

1. Test E-mail, Facsimile and Marine radio communication with Weybourne Atmospheric Observatory. (Can be done at any convenient time during sortie)
2. Transit to operating area at convenient altitude. (45 min)
3. Execute a profile from FL150 to 50 feet in cloud free air if possible. Profile at @1,000 ft/min down to minimum safe altitude. (15 min)
4. Stepped racetrack with 5 minute legs. Initial leg at 100 feet, with 5 more levels to be determined from tephigramme. (45 min)

100 ft	200	500	1000	5000	10000
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5. Execute a profile from 50 ft (or minimum safe altitude) @1,000 ft/min to FL300 (or as high as possible) for Ozone calibration. (30 min)
 6. Transit back to Boscombe Down at convenient altitude. (45 min)
- **TOTAL DURATION:** 3 Hours.
 - **COMMUNICATION REQUIREMENTS:** Marine band for communication with Weybourne Atmospheric Observatory.
 - **DIPLOMATIC:** None.
 - **PRESSURISATION:** Normal pressurisation. (*Please be gentle with our cars.*)

- **TIME TABLE:**

06:30 Weather check (Boscombe Down)

06:45 Go/No Go decision (Telephone call from Farnborough)

08:00 Briefing

08:45 Photographs at Aircraft

09:15 SF26 Safety Brief

09:30 Everyone on aircraft

10:00 Take Off

13:00 Landing

- **SCIENTIFIC CREW: (6+6)**

A/S A Kaye

A/S (training) H Richer

F/L M Rule

Ozone K Dewey

B/F J Kent

Peroxide B Bandy

SF26 S Penkett, B Sturges, R Burgess, C Rceves, L Cardnas, W Broadgate

- **CLOTHING:**

Headsets will be provided. Clothing should be warm and comfortable field clothing, consisting of long trousers, long sleeved shirts and solid lace up shoes. Jewlery and loose items such as coins and keys are not appropriate for the aircraft environment.

A431
27 October 1995
Aircraft Scientist Debrief

Weather Synopsis:

The weather was not ideal, being dominated by a low pressure to the North of Scotland and a pair of cold fronts which were forecast to pass over the operational area during the period of the flight. This resulted in much less stable conditions that had been hoped for.

Flight Summary:

The main objectives of the flight were successful. The ACSOE core group were able to gain first hand experience of MRF C-130 operations. The aircrew were satisfied with the communication links using the marine band radio. A fax was successfully sent from the aircraft to the Weybourne Observatory.

A full set of bottle samples were collected in a stepped racetrack profile just of the coast from the Weybourne Observatory. Due to an in-flight emergency, a cracked flightdeck window, the final level had to be aborted. However once the emergency situation had been sorted a final sample was collected in the region of the final run.

Overall a successful flight.

Problems:

No instrument problems were reported during the flight.

Flightdeck window cracked during flight.

Andrew Kaye

C-130 Communications Links

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kuye

Project: ~~DAIE~~ Date: 7/1/95

Flight No: 431 Page 1 of 3

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
10:03:54	14	/	7500	P	19	51.53	-1.71	Solid SC Below confused horizon broken above.	
10:15:54	14	/	14.9	P	56	52.21	-0.59	Solid SC below some broken in dist. Clear above.	
10:16:21	15	P1	14.9	P	58	52.28	-0.46	"	
10:20:34	15	P1	11,000	P	57	52.43	-0.07	In SC Deck	
10:22:24			9.5	P				Rain on wind glimpses of ground visible.	
10:23:4			8.7	P				Below Cloud.	
10:28		P1 ²⁰⁰⁰	38	P	46	52.75	0.58	heavy.	
10:33:15		P1	10000	R				Clear (clouds) above	
10:34:32								Reconnaissance Profile.	
10:36:45	19	P1 and	50ft	R	30	53.04	1.07	gap in cloud on horizon. (1012 see 4)	
10:47:15	20	R1	100ft	R	352	53.27	1.01	edge of SC sheet above	
								Bottle filled R37 7.25 Bar	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye.

Project: SOLLIE Date: 27/10/95
Flight No: A431 Page 2 of 3

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
						10:44:20	21		
10:51:58	22	R2	200ft		197	53.30	1.15	R4 7.25 Bar.	
10:56:58	23	R2 ^{P.2}	200	R	197	53.01	1.05	Broken cu to east clear to west.	
10:58:49	25	R3	500		352	53.05	0.97	Sc to east Sc ahead. clear above.	
								Bottle. R29 7.25 Bar	
11:03:51	26	R3 ^{P.23}	500	R	343	53.38	0.91	Hazy below sc ahead clear above.	
11:05:50	28	R4	1000	R	381	53.36	1.02	haze layer ahead sun on water broken cu ahead.	
11:10:59	29	R4 ^{P.24}	1000	R	174	53.04	1.12	R2 7.3 Bar	
11:15:42	32	R5	5000	R	346	53.07	1.01	very small scattered cu below clear above.	
11:20:59	37	R5 ^{end}	5000	R	346	53.37	0.96	Small cu below H3 ^{R5} 7.23 Bar	
11:23:52		P2.5	10000					recurrence profile.	
								BROKEN WINDOW end of Science.	

R5 - 7.23 Bar
A. Kaye

Fax TO Weybourne 01263-588153

→ ETA Weybourne 10:30

use Marine band channel 10

Here call sign Met Man 74

W.A.O. call sign WEYBOURNE.

E-mail Derek & relay message by telephone.

01263 588154

✓ sent
successfully

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: A431

Date: 27 10.95

A/S Name: A. KAYE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period *indef.*
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project *ACSOE*
4. Do you want the video tape kept? -
YES NO How long? *indefinitely + 1 copy*
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in? *MRF 8: [mfd.a431]*
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT
 =====

FLIGHT NO: A431

DATE: 27/10 A5

MRF

INSTRUMENT	FITTED		OPERATED		COMMENTS
	YES	NO	YES	NO	
NAVIGATION: GPS OMEGA INU RADALT	☒	☐	☒	☐	
THERMOMETERS: DI TEMP NDI TEMP ICTP BARNES PRT4	☒	☐	☒	☐	
HYGROMETERS: GEN. EASTERN TWC FWVS J/W	☒	☐	☒	☐	
EXP. PITOT HEAD: STATIC PRESS. PITOT PRESS. GUST VANES	☒	☐	☒	☐	
RADIOMETERS: UPPER CLEAR UPPER RED UPPER SILICON LOWER CLEAR LOWER RED LOWER SILICON MARSS MCR/SAFIRE DEIMOS	☒	☐	☒	☒	
CHEMISTRY: OZONE ECGC NOX	☐	☐	☒	☒	
OTHERS: CCN CLOUD PHYSICS CABIN PRESS NEPHELOMETER HOLOGRAPHY	☒	☐	☒	☒	

P. T. O. FAULTS/INCIDENTS

FLIGHT LEADER'S IN-FLIGHT LOG

Date 27 10.95 Flight No. A431

Page 1 of 2

VIDEO TAPE

No. A431
Ends 1310

- DFC
- RFC
- FFC

	GPS	INU
Lat.	<u>53'14.5</u>	<u>53'15.93</u>
Long.	<u>+1'04.06E</u>	<u>14.13E</u>
Time	<u>112014</u>	<u>112029</u>

DRS recording to HORACE

HORACE recording to optical disk

SATCOM sending position reports

Time GMT	Event No	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.		
<u>080462</u>		<u>START</u>	<u>RECORDING</u>				<u>GPS</u>	<u>start</u>	<u>51' 09.83 N</u>		
							<u>Position</u>		<u>-001' 44.66 E</u>		
<u>094055</u>		<u>INU</u>	<u>TO NAVIGATE</u>								
<u>095705</u>		<u>TAKE OFF</u>	<u>FROM</u>	<u>BOSCOMBE</u>							
<u>101148</u>		<u>START</u>	<u>VIDEO</u>								
			<u>START PROFILE</u>	<u>P1 ↓</u>			<u>1000ft min</u>				
<u>101721</u>	<u>15</u>	<u>FUSO</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>060</u>							
<u>102803</u>	<u>16.</u>	<u>4000ft</u>	<u>change rate of descent to 500ft/min</u>								
		<u>Interupt</u>	<u>PROF</u>	<u>PROFILE P1</u>							
<u>103315</u>	<u>17</u>	<u>1000ft</u>	<u>1012</u>								
<u>103432</u>	<u>18</u>	<u>1000ft</u>	<u>1012</u>	<u>035</u>	<u>Recommence profile P1</u>						
<u>103643</u>	<u>19</u>	<u>50ft</u>	<u>1012</u>	<u>030</u>	<u>END</u>	<u>PROFILE P1</u>			<u>sea state 4</u>	<u>270/18</u>	
			<u>START</u>	<u>RUN</u>	<u>1</u>						
<u>104428</u>	<u>20</u>	<u>100ft</u>	<u>1012</u>	<u>355</u>							
<u>104409</u>		<u>Heimann</u>	<u>cal</u>	<u>10 →</u>	<u>ISC</u>						
<u>104800</u>		<u>1st bottle</u>	<u>R37</u>	<u>filled</u>							
			<u>END</u>	<u>RUN</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>START PROFILE P2.1 ↑</u>					
<u>104920</u>	<u>21</u>	<u>100ft</u>	<u>1012</u>	<u>355</u>		<u>12.3</u>	<u>6.9</u>	<u>OFF.</u>			
<u>104940</u>	<u>21</u>	<u>END</u>	<u>PROFILE P2.1</u>								
		<u>↓</u>	<u>START</u>	<u>RUN</u>	<u>2.</u>						
<u>105158</u>	<u>22</u>	<u>200ft</u>	<u>1012.</u>	<u>200</u>	<u>190</u>	<u>96</u>	<u>12.0</u>	<u>6.2</u>			

HERCULES VIDEO TAPE LOG

FLIGHT NO. A 431PROJECT (Narc JOLLIE) ref A.C.S.O.E.DATE 27 : 10 : 95TAPE NO. A431USER J KayeRETENTION PERIOD Indefinite

GMT	TAPE COUNTER	CAMERA POSITION	REMARKS
101148		FFC	START RECORDING
101721 → 103643		"	PROFILE #1 ↓, FL150 → 50ft
104428 → 104920		"	RUN 1, 100ft
105158 → 105658		"	RUN 2, 200ft
105848 → 110349		"	RUN 3, 500ft
10551 → 111055		"	RUN 4, 1000ft
11542 → 112059		"	RUN 5, 5000ft
1127		"	Flight deck window cracked, descend from FL100. Abort Sortie
		"	Transit to Boscombe at FL60
22148		"	Land at Boscombe
22810			STOP RECORDING

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A431 Date: 27.10.95

Page...!...of 1

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0848	REF -	5	568	✓		Approx	0568
	REF -	7	3071	✓		Approx	3071
	AOSS	19	✓	FOR F/S STRD O/S	TORQUE 2.5		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	✓	UP F/S DOWN D/S	TORQUE 3-3.5		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	0			As Indicated	0000
	PR HT	8	3847	998	1000	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3955	997	✓		
	A/S	9	42	✓		As ASI	0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	264	40	41		
	UP2S	82	221	15	16		
	UIRS	83	2016	-9	376		
	UP1Z	84	146	✓		Approx	0147
	UP2Z	85	148	✓		Approx	0149
	UIRZ	86	2041	✓		Approx	2061
	UP1T	87	2603	+12	12.2	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2615	+11		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	2635	+10		As IAT	
	LP1S	91	101	-20			
	LP2S	92					
	LIRS	93					
	LP1Z	94				Approx	0150
	LP2Z	95				Approx	0146
	LIRZ	96				Approx	2050
	LP1T	97				As IAT	
	LP2T	98				As IAT	
	LIRT	99				As IAT	
	J/W	42	996	0	✓	As Indicated	0000
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58	2779	9.4	✓		
	HYCC	59	699	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138	4095			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	*				
	DTF	10	3306				
	DTC	11	5	+12	✓		
	NDTF	23	3096			same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5	+12			
	INCT	48	4095				
	CCN	140	4095			less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	2154			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	103			0640-1860	< min
	O3	100	0				
	O3P	106	1551			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1886				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
0856	FL NO	1	Hex	431	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	085	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	534	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	12			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
				4095	not filled		
	LATC	160	Dec	582			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	000			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70				0001-4095	
	TNOS	71				2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72				0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73				2400-3200	
	TSRC	74				2160-2470	
	HTR1	75				0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76				0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77				0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78				4095	
	EV1V	170					
	EV2V	171					
	NPWR	172					
	EVIC	173					
	EV2C	174					

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	☒ Off / On	Large ☒ Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	☒ Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

A431

27-OCT-95

11:15:18

031 Ω 53.01

1.03 AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
348.	856.	4.6	193.	2.0	-5.3	279/13

PHGTF
Kft

4.59

OZMR
ppb

49.15

15.00

15.00

12.50

12.50

10.00

10.00

7.50

7.50

5.00

5.00

2.50

2.50

0.00

0.00

0.00

12.50

25.00

37.50

50.00

62.50

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A431

27-OCT-95

10:41:36

019 Ω

52.87

1.17 AS P

HDG degT	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
359.	997.	0.4	201.	11.1	6.2	266/10

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

HRS degT	CDP mb	PHGT Kft	TAC knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
180.	1001.	0.3	195.	11.6	6.2	267/13

PHGT
Kft: 0.34 SPP
mb: 1001.03

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms:	Form Title
1	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet
3	Aircraft Scientist log
1	Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements
1	Interactive log
1	Flight Leader pre-flight check form
1	Flight Leader in-flight check form
2	Flight Leader in-flight log
1	Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	MCR log
	CCN log
	MARSS log
1	Chemistry log - Ozone
1	Bottle Samplers Log
	Particulate/Filter boom Operator's log
	2DK/FSSP/Holography Operator's log
	Sonde Ejector's log
	Navigator's log
	Photographic log (photocopy original)
✓	Instrument status forms
✓	RTD prints
✓	Raw data plots
✓	Signal register
✓	Weather charts
✓	Satellite pictures
	Omega track
	Electronics pre-flight
	Mechanical fit

SURFACE ANALYSIS
VT 0001 U.T.C.
DATE 27 OCT 19 95
ISSUED BY HOSTC AT 27 0330
SCALE 1 : 20 000 000
CHART STC 1

976

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE IN KNOTS
4 MB INTERVAL

SCALE OF NAUTICAL MILES

SURFACE WIND PROG.
 1800 U.T.C.
 DATE 27 OCT 19 95
 ISSUED BY HOSTC AT 27 00Z
 SCALE 1:20 000 000
 CHART STC 1

016

FORECASTER B. Perreault

ANDY_T951027.TXT

From 0Z 22/10/1995 to 12Z 27/10/1995

Arrows every 24 hrs

Plotted 30-Oct-1995 16:13

A431 27-OCT-95

A431 27-OCT-95 10:17:00-11:27:00GMT

mercator projection

GPS TRACK - run no

A431 27-OCT-95 Height time series

A431 Profile 1

| Temperature

| Dew Point

A431 27-OCT-95 Profile P1

Times 10:17:21-10:36:43 GMT

1 second averages

A431 27-OCT-95 Profile P1

Times 10:17:21-10:36:43 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A431 27-OCT-95 Profile P1

Times 10:17:21-10:36:43 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A431 27-OCT-95

Run no. R1

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 293
Mean 53.1625
Standard dev 7.264583e-02
Max value 53.2887
Min value 53.0358

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 293
Mean 1.10336
Standard dev 3.195075e-03
Max value 1.11169
Min value 1.09953

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 293
Mean 285.417
Standard dev 7.350218e-02
Max value 285.556
Min value 285.263

1 second averages

10:44:28 10:45:41 10:46:54 10:48:07 10:49:20
TIME (GMT)

A431 27-OCT-95

Run no. R1

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 293
Mean 30.7419
Standard dev 1.44138
Max value 34.6368
Min value 26.6473

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 293
Mean 34.6423
Standard dev 1.58083
Max value 39.4551
Min value 31.5681

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 293
Mean 279.764
Standard dev 0.344265
Max value 280.569
Min value 278.976

1 second averages

A431 27-OCT-95

Run no. R1

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 293
Mean 5.66875
Standard dev 0.190944
Max value 6.05389
Min value 5.11259

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 293
Mean 240.093
Standard dev 54.9728
Max value 423.901
Min value 123.144

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 293
Mean 8.834581e-02
Standard dev 3.128698e-03
Max value 9.915963e-02
Min value 8.101994e-02

1 second averages

A431 27-OCT-95

Run no. R2

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 301
Mean 53.2203
Standard dev 7.065045e-02
Max value 53.3426
Min value 53.0990

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 301
Mean 1.11503
Standard dev 2.202245e-02
Max value 1.15520
Min value 1.07868

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 301
Mean 285.025
Standard dev 5.344012e-02
Max value 285.166
Min value 284.906

1 second averages

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Run no. R2

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 301
Mean 62.2115
Standard dev 2.71073
Max value 68.6386
Min value 57.6763

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 301
Mean 66.9450
Standard dev 2.36199
Max value 72.8981
Min value 61.8528

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 301
Mean 279.563
Standard dev 0.329329
Max value 280.529
Min value 278.592

1 second averages

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Run no. R2

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 301
Mean 5.22386
Standard dev 0.203874
Max value 5.65636
Min value 4.49924

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 301
Mean 289.837
Standard dev 79.7324
Max value 605.602
Min value 148.958

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 301
Mean 8.838770e-02
Standard dev 3.316907e-03
Max value 0.105956
Min value 8.136046e-02

1 second averages

A431 27-OCT-95

Run no. R3

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 302
Mean 53.2033
Standard dev 7.326378e-02
Max value 53.3306
Min value 53.0767

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 302
Mean 0.997092
Standard dev 1.349065e-02
Max value 1.01761
Min value 0.973252

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 302
Mean 284.091
Standard dev 7.183187e-02
Max value 284.310
Min value 283.956

10:58:48 11:00:03 11:01:18 11:02:33 11:03:49

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

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Run no. R3

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 302
Mean 146.481
Standard dev 2.11956
Max value 151.507
Min value 141.845

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 302
Mean 149.369
Standard dev 1.77080
Max value 153.571
Min value 144.844

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 302
Mean 279.360
Standard dev 0.324659
Max value 280.145
Min value 278.560

1 second averages

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Run no. R3

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 302
Mean 5.04816
Standard dev 9.579881e-02
Max value 5.28380
Min value 4.79996

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 302
Mean 273.583
Standard dev 51.0566
Max value 465.162
Min value 149.965

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 302
Mean 9.000648e-02
Standard dev 2.866551e-03
Max value 9.873945e-02
Min value 8.426085e-02

1 second averages

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Run no. R4

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 305
Mean 53.2406
Standard dev 7.509913e-02
Max value 53.3696
Min value 53.1102

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 305
Mean 1.07059
Standard dev 2.466345e-02
Max value 1.11416
Min value 1.03036

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 305
Mean 282.537
Standard dev 9.166547e-02
Max value 283.185
Min value 282.389

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A431 27-OCT-95

Run no. R4

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 305
Mean 313.990
Standard dev 3.31549
Max value 320.773
Min value 301.078

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 305
Mean 317.630
Standard dev 2.52849
Max value 322.827
Min value 307.115

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 305
Mean 278.417
Standard dev 0.702881
Max value 279.648
Min value 275.448

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A431 27-OCT-95

Run no. R4

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 305
Mean 5.15709
Standard dev 0.213924
Max value 5.67533
Min value 4.67541

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 305
Mean 310.544
Standard dev 52.7806
Max value 471.405
Min value 158.267

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 305
Mean 9.260032e-02
Standard dev 3.366425e-03
Max value 0.103082
Min value 8.535650e-02

1 second averages

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Run no. R5

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

11:15:42 11:17:01 11:18:20 11:19:39 11:20:00
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A431 27-OCT-95

Run no. R5

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 318
Mean 1511.72
Standard dev 7.39251
Max value 1521.61
Min value 1493.19

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 318
Mean 1522.49
Standard dev 8.60737
Max value 1544.22
Min value 1503.75

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 318
Mean 266.598
Standard dev 0.514612
Max value 267.960
Min value 265.446

1 second averages

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Run no. R5

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 318
Mean 6.39152
Standard dev 1.09448
Max value 7.01215
Min value 3.27896

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 318
Mean 13.4262
Standard dev 6.99538
Max value 45.0293
Min value 1.00000

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 318
Mean 0.101358
Standard dev 1.683443e-02
Max value 0.195550
Min value 6.221665e-02

1 second averages